

EXPLORATORY RESEARCH ON THE ADVANCED UTILIZATION OF BERRY BY-PRODUCTS. CASE STUDY: SEA BUCKTHORN

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Abstract

The paper explores the potential of using by-products resulted from the processing of sea buckthorn fruits (*Hippophae rhamnoides*) in the bakery industry, as an example of applying the principles of circular economy. The study highlights the nutritional value of sea buckthorn, which is rich in vitamins, antioxidants and fibre, and analyses the impact of adding sea buckthorn powder to bread on the sensory and physico-chemical properties of the final product. The bread samples were prepared with various additions of sea buckthorn powder (1%, 3%, 5%), and the sensory analysis revealed that an addition of 1% improves the taste, aroma and texture of the bread, keeping a high level of acceptability. The results suggest that sea buckthorn by-products can be successfully integrated into bakery, helping to reduce waste and create functional food products in line with sustainability goals. This research highlights both the economic and ecological benefits of leveraging local resources in the food industry.

Keywords: sea buckthorn, mountain circular economy, by-products, bakery, sustainability

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The role of berries in the bioeconomy of mountainous areas in Romania

Berries play an important role in the bioeconomy of mountainous areas in Romania, contributing significantly to the sustainable development of these regions, from an economic, ecological and social point of view. This activity addresses several aspects of the circular economy and can support the revitalization of mountain communities by harnessing natural resources in a sustainable way. The mountainous areas in Romania, such as the Southern, Eastern and Western Carpathians, are characterized by deciduous and coniferous forests, which are the habitat of some forest fruit species such as blueberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus*), raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*), blackberry (*Rubus fruticosus*), currant (*Ribes spp.*), sea buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides*), and others. They are harvested both for domestic consumption and for export, with a growing demand in international markets due to their health benefits (antioxidants, vitamins, minerals). Berries are well known as fruits with health benefits (Reynoso-Camacho et al. 2021), containing high amounts of different bioactive compounds such as tannins, anthocyanins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds and organic acids (Jimenez-Garcia et al. 2013). The waste resulting from their processing can be further utilized in bioactive compounds, which can later be used as functional ingredients (El-Sawi et al. 2021).

The production of forest fruits in Romania can be divided into two categories: cultivated production and spontaneous production, each with its own particularities.

Cultivated production (FAOSTAT 2023).

- Blueberries – Cultivated blueberries are the leader in the berry market, due to high demand on the domestic and foreign markets. Cultivated areas have increased significantly, from 400 hectares in 2020 to 800 hectares in 2022, and production has exceeded 3,300 tons.
- Raspberries – Raspberries are a valuable crop, but cultivated areas are smaller, about 90 hectares in 2022, with a total production of 170 tons.
- Blackberries – Although less extensive than blueberries or raspberries, blackberry crops are expanding, being appreciated for the introduction of modern varieties that offer higher yields and quality.
- Strawberries – They have the largest share of all cultivated berries, with a production of more than 17,600 tonnes in 2022, but the trend is downwards due to competition and production costs.

Spontaneous production from the mountain area

Spontaneous production is specific to the mountain forests of the Carpathians, where blueberries, blackberries, raspberries and currants grow naturally. These fruits are mainly harvested by local communities, and a significant part is collected by specialized companies for export.

- Wild blueberries are the most harvested forest fruits in mountain areas, being valued for their superior quality compared to cultivated ones. Annual spontaneous production is estimated to exceed 10,000 tonnes.
- Raspberries and wild blackberries are also harvested intensively, but in smaller quantities due to limited accessibility in mountainous areas.
- Currants and sea buckthorn complete this category, being less harvested, but in high demand for industrial processing.

Spontaneous production contributes to biodiversity, but its exploitation must be carried out responsibly to avoid the degradation of natural ecosystems. Harvesting, processing and marketing of berries can contribute significantly to the local economy, stimulating jobs in rural areas where industrial activities are often limited. The production of jams, juices, syrups, or even pharmaceutical products based on these fruits can generate considerable income for small farmers and local cooperatives (George, Cenkowski 2005).

Berries are a renewable resource and an ecologically sustainable alternative to other types of intensive agriculture. Harvesting them from the natural environment, without affecting the ecosystems, supports the principles of the circular economy and reduces the negative impact on the environment, compared to traditional agricultural crops. Mountain forests, especially in protected areas or nature parks, are essential for maintaining the ecological balance. Also, the promotion of berries can help combat soil erosion and protect mountain lands from landslides, having a positive impact on the sustainability of mountain ecosystems. Berries provide opportunities for mountain communities to develop small businesses and diversify their sources of income. Cooperation projects between local

producers, local authorities and development organizations can help to form business networks and raise living standards. In addition, harvesting and processing berries can stimulate education and training in areas such as sustainable mountain agriculture, food processing and marketing of traditional products.

Large amounts of by-products come from fruit processing, especially from the juice industry, including leaves, peels, pulp, seeds, and much of this material is ultimately discarded. The transformation of these wastes into high-value food products could reduce losses, using the by-products as sources of bioactive compounds, which can be applied in the development of functional products (Marcillo-Parra et al. 2021). Moreover, there is a growing interest in identifying sources rich in polyphenols, for the development of functional beverages and food products or for the development of food supplements (Reynoso-Camacho et al. 2021; Zheng et al. 2017).

The natural juice industry has become a strategic direction for the valorisation of forest fruits, contributing to increasing the added value of these resources. Natural juices, obtained from fresh fruit, without added sugar or preservatives, blueberry, raspberry, blackberry or sea buckthorn juices are increasingly popular due to the interest in a healthy lifestyle. More and more products are ecologically certified, which makes them attractive to foreign markets.

Among the most important producers we can mention:

- *Profructta* produces natural juices from organic fruits, promoting the quality and authenticity of Romanian products.
- *Romsilva* developed an infrastructure for the processing of forest fruits from the state's forests, the products being intended for both domestic market and export.

Although Romania produces large quantities of forest fruits, most of them are exported as raw material, which limits the added value generated locally. Due to insufficient investment, processing capacity is still low, and many regions lack the necessary infrastructure to develop the juice industry. Natural products from Romania are appreciated for their quality, and the expansion of juice exports represents a major opportunity.

The superior valorisation of berries also includes the use of by-products resulting from their traditional processing to obtain berry juices. Globally, by-products are a significant source of pollution: food losses and waste occur throughout the food supply chain, representing around 16% of the total food supply (Marcillo-Parra et al. 2021).

In the juice production process, between 30% and 50% of the fruit mass becomes waste, consisting of peels, seeds and residual pulp. By category of forest fruits, the estimated amounts of waste are:

- Blueberries – Waste: ~30%-40% of total mass processed. At a production of 3,300 tons, 1,000-1,300 tons of organic waste results.
- Raspberries – Waste: ~35%-45%. Out of 170 tons of raspberries, about 60-75 tons become waste.
- Blackberries – Waste: ~30%-40%. At an estimated 500-tons, 150-200 tons of waste results.
- Sea Buckthorn – Waste: ~40%-50%. From a production of 1,000 tons, 400-500 tons of waste is generated.

- Currants and others – Waste: ~30%-40%. At a production of 200 tons, 60-80 tons of waste is generated.

The main waste recovery methods in the berry juice processing industry are:

Composting and biogas: Waste is turned into compost to fertilize agricultural soils or used to produce renewable energy through biogas plants.

Antioxidant extracts: The pulp and peels can be processed to obtain extracts rich in polyphenols and antioxidants, used in the food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries.

Fortification of bakery products: An innovative and sustainable use of berry waste is its integration into bakery products. The dietary fibre and antioxidants present in these wastes are used to enrich products such as bread, biscuits and cakes. These additions provide the following benefits:

- Increased nutritional value – Baked goods become richer in fibre, antioxidants and minerals, contributing to digestive health and reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease.
- Natural Flavors – The seeds and pulp add a subtle, natural berry flavour.
- Colour and texture – Peels and pulp give a distinctive appearance to products, making them more attractive to consumers.

Animal feed: Waste can be processed for animal feed, being a natural source of fibre and nutrients for livestock farms.

Production of energy pellets: Dry organic residues can be used for the production of pellets, helping to reduce the consumption of conventional fuels.

The purpose of this work is to analyse the use of by-products resulting from the production of sea buckthorn juice for the fortification of bakery products. Sea buckthorn, scientifically called *Hippophae Rhamnoides*, is a fruit-bearing shrub native to Central Asia, with fruits recognized for their nutritional value and beneficial properties. The branchy and thorny shrub is between 2 and 6 meters tall, and its grey-green leaves are elongated and narrow. The small flowers appear before the leaves, and the fruits, initially green, turn yellow-orange as they ripen, measuring about 1 cm.

Sea buckthorn fruits are mainly used in various industries, such as food, pharmaceutical, forestry or as ornamental plants. They are considered true “natural multivitamins” due to their rich nutrient content and varied uses in medicine and food. They are processed in the form of juices, jams, jellies, syrups and liqueurs, being recognized as general tonic foods for the body.

In addition to the fruits, other parts of the shrub, such as the leaves (rich in vitamin C), the buds and the bark, are used for the preparation of various products, thus expanding the possibilities of harnessing the sea buckthorn. This wide potential of use makes sea buckthorn by-products a valuable candidate for improving the nutritional and sensory properties of bakery products. Sea buckthorn is recognized as one of the richest natural sources of vitamin C, with an impressive concentration of up to 700 mg/100 g. In addition, it contains a wide range of essential nutrients, including:

- **Vitamins:** vitamin A, vitamin B complex (B1, B2, B6, B9, choline, inositol), vitamins E, K, P and F.
- **Minerals and trace elements:** calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, potassium, iron and sodium.

- **Bioactive compounds:** carotenoids (beta-carotene, in higher concentrations than in carrots, and xanthophyll), flavonoids, polyphenols with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, serotonin, tannins and phytosterols.
- **Essential fatty acids:** Omega-3, Omega-6 and Omega-9, present in the oil extracted from the seeds.
- **Oils and enzymes:** complex oils (from which sea buckthorn oil is produced), volatile oils and active enzymes.
- **Dietary fibre:** the peel and pulp of the fruit contain beneficial fibre for digestive health.

Due to its rich composition, sea buckthorn is a true source of essential nutrients, being used both in food and in medicine, due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and tonic effects on the body (Lougas 2006).

Fig. 1. Sea buckthorn fruits

By-products from the processing of sea buckthorn berries include:

- **Seeds:** rich in essential oils and antioxidants.
- **Pulp and peel:** sources of dietary fibre, pectin and carotenoids.
- **Leaves:** contain compounds with therapeutic potential, including flavonoids and tannins.

These by-products can be used for the development of functional foods, nutritional supplements, cosmetics and natural medicines. Recently, the bakery industry has shown increased interest in using these by-products as functional ingredients.

Table 1 shows a series of characteristics that the sea buckthorn fruit powder contains (Ghendov 2020).

Table 1. General characteristics of sea buckthorn powder

Characteristics of sea buckthorn powder	Values
Humidity, %.	7.80 ± 0.20
Ascorbic acid, mg / 100 g	352.5 ± 23.4
Total polyphenol content (Folin-Ciocalteu), mg GAE / 100 g	1467 ± 471
Total polyphenol content (Abs280), mg GAE / 100 g	1311 ± 105
Total flavonoid content, mg GAE / 100 g	555 ± 61
Cinnamic acids, mg CAE / 100 g	425 ± 34
Flavonols, mg QE / 100 g	668 ± 33
Total carotenoid content, mg / 100 g	34.93 ± 1.30
Catechin, mg / 100 g	35.3 ± 5.1
Hyperoside, mg / 100 g	23.6 ± 12.1
Chlorogenic acid, mg / 100 g	11.1 ± 6.3
Cis-resveratrol, mg / 100 g	10.8 ± 7.5
Trans-resveratrol, mg / 100 g	10.4 ± 0.4
Ferulic acid, mg / 100 g	10.3 ± 1.6
Protocatechuic acid, mg / 100 g	7.0 ± 0.9
Procyanidins B2, mg / 100 g	4.3 ± 1.7
Epicatechin, mg / 100 g	2.5 ± 1.8
Gallic acid, mg / 100 g	2.2 ± 0.5
Procyanidins B1, mg / 100 g	1.6 ± 0.2
Quercetin, mg / 100 g	0.9 ± 0.8
p-hydroxybenzoic acid, mg / 100 g	0.8 ± 0.2
Syringic acid, mg / 100 g	0.7 ± 0.3
m-hydroxybenzoic acid, mg / 100 g	0.5 ± 0.1
Vanillic acid, mg / 100 g	0.5 ± 0.2
p-coumaric acid, mg / 100 g	0.3 ± 0.2
Caffeic acid, mg / 100 g	0.2 ± 0.0

1.2. Sanogenic properties of sea buckthorn berries

Sea buckthorn berries are an excellent source of bioactive compounds that support the proven health benefits of sea buckthorn juice and oil. They contain soluble vitamins, antioxidants such as vitamins C and E, β -carotene and lycopene, essential fatty acids, amino acids, phytosterols, flavonoids and important minerals such as iron and calcium (Luntrararu et al. 2022). They are used in about 200 industrial processes, including the production of drugs and herbs, for the treatment of cancer, heart disease, ulcers, liver disorders, burns and brain problems. The most valuable components of sea buckthorn berries are the oils, having a high content of lipids both in the seeds and in the pulp. These include tocopherols, tocotrienols, carotenoids, as well as fatty acids from the omega-3 and omega-6 families (Piłat, Bieniek, Zadernowski 2014).

The antioxidants in sea buckthorn, in the form of a series of phenolic compounds, help reduce oxidative stress and prevent cell degeneration. Due to the high content of vitamin C and zinc, sea buckthorn berries have important benefits in preventing colds and other infections by stimulating and regulating the function of the immune system. Sea

buckthorn extract is effective in the prevention and treatment of diabetes, having a significant role in regulating blood sugar. Sea buckthorn treatments are also beneficial for the digestive system, relieving the symptoms of irritable bowel syndrome and chronic constipation. Sea buckthorn berries are low in saturated fat, but provide a significant amount of omega-6 fatty acids, which help reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease.

Sea buckthorn is also an important source of essential minerals, such as potassium, iron, magnesium and zinc, contributing to maintaining the body's mineral balance and supporting the correct functioning of vital systems and organs. Regarding the processing of sea buckthorn by-products, it involves technologies such as solvent extraction, supercritical fluids and micro-encapsulation, which allow the recovery of active compounds and improve their stability.

1.3. Designing functional bakery products with the addition of sea buckthorn by-products

Functional food is defined as a food that benefits one or more functions of the body, beyond the basic nutritional effects, contributing to improving health, well-being or reducing the risk of disease. It is consumed as part of a regular diet. Creating a functional food product involves changing the nutritional composition of the food. Typically, intervention on the composition of conventional foods is achieved through three main methods (Diaconescu 2005; Niva 2008, Apostol 2015):

- content enrichment in (for example, foods rich in dietary fibre, or foods fortified with calcium or magnesium);
- diminishing content in (for example, foods low in salt or saturated fat);
- replacing the component ... with (for example, sugar is replaced by low glycemic index sweeteners, such as inulin).

The by-products obtained from the processing of sea buckthorn fruits are successfully used in the bakery industry due to their nutritional and functional benefits:

- Sea buckthorn bark flour: adds fibre, vitamins and antioxidants to wholemeal bread, crackers or cookies.
- Buckthorn pulp: can be used to replace fat in muffin and cake recipes.
- Sea buckthorn seeds: ground or in the form of oil, they are used to improve the characteristics of the product and make them crunchier, and they bring an intake of healthy fatty acids.
- Natural colours and flavours: sea buckthorn carotenoids naturally colour baked goods, making them more attractive.

2. MATERIALS, EQUIPMENT AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1. Used raw materials

Bread samples were obtained with a replacement degree of 1%, 3% and 5% sea buckthorn powder, containing a mix of seeds and epicarp of dried and ground sea buckthorn fruits, to determine its effect on sensory and physico-chemical parameters of breads. The amount of wheat flour was replaced with an equal amount of sea buckthorn

flour. The control sample was prepared without the addition of sea buckthorn, and the following ingredients were used to make the bread: high-quality wheat flour from Moara de Familie (Table 2), dry yeast (Belbake), iodized salt (Salrom from Romania), white sugar (Coronița), dry and ground organic sea buckthorn powder (Niavis) and drinking water at room temperature (Fig. 2).

Table 2. Physico-chemical indicators of wheat flour used in the manufacture of bread.

Parameters	Values
Humidity (%)	12.01 ± 0.1
Ash content (%)	0.480 ± 0.001
Moist gluten content (%)	24.52 ± 0.2
Acidity (acidity degrees)	2.0 ± 0.1

2.2. The dough preparation method

The direct method was used to prepare the dough, which involves mixing all the ingredients in the recipe in one step. The dough is kneaded for 15 minutes using classic mixers, then left to ferment for 45 minutes at a temperature of 30-32°C, using an amount of yeast between 1.5% and 3%. The duration of fermentation varies according to the amount of yeast: a smaller amount prolongs the process, while a larger amount reduces the ripening time. This is due to the carbon dioxide released, which influences the stretch of the gluten network. Table 3 shows the recipes of the 4 samples used in the experimental research (Fig. 3).

Table 3. The amount of ingredients used in the recipe

P0 (control sample)	P1 (replacement degree of 1%)	P2 (replacement degree of 3%)	P3 (replacement degree of 5%)
400g wheat flour	396 g wheat flour	388 g wheat flour	380 g wheat flour
0 g sea buckthorn flour	4 g sea buckthorn flour	12 g sea buckthorn flour	20 g sea buckthorn flour
8 g yeast	8 g yeast	8 g yeast	8 g yeast
8 g salt	8 g salt	8 g salt	8 g salt
12 g sugar	12 g sugar	12 g sugar	12 g sugar
300 ml water	280 ml water	270 ml water	260 ml water

2.3. Equipment's used

For the manufacture of bakery products with the addition of sea buckthorn, the equipment from the bakery laboratory of the Faculty of Food and Tourism of Transilvania University in Brașov was used. The technological line is composed of: SF100 flour sifter, Silver50 type mixer, SQ20 dough dividing machine, T1 round shape shaping machine, RO-CR-600 long shape shaping machine, TELBO type dough proofer and oven with steam type RING model MSR 4 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Equipment used to obtain the studied bakery products

2.4. Sensory analysis method of experimental breads

Sensory analysis is a method of evaluating the characteristics and quality of food products, based on knowledge from various scientific fields, such as neurophysiology, human physiology, sociology, statistics and psychology (Lawless Harry, Heymann 2010). The sensory attributes of food products are essential factors that influence the purchase and consumption decision. To test the obtained products, the method of acceptance tests was used, which involves collecting the answers of a group of tasters to questions about the degree of satisfaction, such as: "How much do you like this product?". This method makes it easier to assess consumer preferences and identify potential product improvements (Lawless, Heymann 2010). The evaluation uses a hedonic scale with nine points and nine possible ratings for the evaluated product, ranging from "I like it very much" to "I dislike it very much".

The sensory analysis methods used to test the obtained products were the following: the rating scale method and the acceptance test method. The rating scale method consists in using requirements to assess the intensity of a sensory property or characteristic (sensory attribute). This method is widely applied and used for the quantitative evaluation of a set of organoleptic properties (appearance, smell, taste, colour, etc.) of food products (Lawless, Heymann 2010). The first stage of the sensory method is to establish the team of evaluators (panel), through selection based on a questionnaire, followed by the training of the panel for the sensory evaluation of the products subject to testing.

The second stage consists in the elaboration of the sensory analysis sheet. After the individual evaluation, the sensory analysis sheets are centralized and a calculation method is applied to evaluate the results. If the evaluation panel consists of N evaluators and n is the number of sensory attributes set for evaluation, it follows that each product sample will receive a total of $(N \times n)$ scores (appreciations), i.e. each evaluator gives one score to each evaluation criterion (attribute) for each of the samples analysed and tasted. The total score (P_{tot}) i that a sensory feature "i" receives from all "N" evaluators is given by formula 1.1:

$$(P_{tot})_i = \sum_{j=1}^N (P_{indi})_j = P_{ind1} + P_{ind2} + \dots + P_{indN} \quad (1.1)$$

where:

$(P_{indi})_j$ - is the individual score given by rater "j" for the feature „i”;

N - the total number of evaluators in the panel.

The average score that characteristic “I” receives is given by formula 1.2.

$$(P_{med})_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (P_{ind}i)_j}{N} = \frac{(P_{ind1} + P_{ind2} + \dots + P_{ind N})}{N} \quad (1.2)$$

For the analysis of the sensory characteristics in the evaluation sheet, several scoring systems are used, of which we used the 5-point evaluation system. The sensory analysis method used to test the obtained products was the acceptance test method, which consists of analysing the responses of groups of tasters to a series of questions related to “How much do you like this product?” (Lawless, Heymann 2010).

The evaluation uses a hedonic scale with nine points and nine possible ratings for the evaluated product, ranging from “I like it very much” to “I dislike it very much”.

Regarding crust evaluation, the bread was sliced and served to the panel members, so attributes such as crust volume and colour are more visible and distinct and can be evaluated both compared to the control sample and between samples with different additions.

Regarding the evaluation of the core, the bread slices were examined by an overall evaluation, taking into account the porosity of the core, its elasticity and its colour.

In order to evaluate the taste and texture, each participant received a slice of bread on a neutral-coloured support (white in advance) in order to evaluate the texture, crumbliness, specific taste and aftertaste.

3. RESULTS

The results of the analysis of the bread samples with the addition of sea buckthorn powder are presented in table 4.

Table 4. The grades of the studies bread products

Indicators	Maximum score	P0 - Control sample	P1 - 1%	P2 - 3%	P3 - 5%
Volume	24	20	18	15	14
Height of marginal cracks	7	6	5	5	4
Crust colour	7	6	6	5	5
Crumb colour	10	9	8	8	7
Porosity	20	20	18	17	16
Elasticity	20	18	16	16	14
Flavour	12	12	10	9	6
Total	100	91	81	75	66

The results of the sensory analysis revealed that the addition of 1% and 3% sea buckthorn powder considerably improved the organoleptic qualities of the obtained products. These samples were distinguished by a smooth, glossy crust of yellowish-brown colour, an elastic crumb, a specific texture, a well-developed porosity and a pleasant taste and aroma. The score obtained by samples P1 and P2 for the organoleptic analysis is in the range of 75-81, indicating that the products are considered acceptable from a sensory point of view. In contrast, the sample with 5% (sample P3) sea buckthorn powder showed

a darker crust, dry crumbs, poorly developed porosity, and the taste and aroma were typical of sea buckthorn fruits.

Table number 5 shows the results obtained from the scores given to the sensory analysis sheets. The following sensory analysis methods were used to test the obtained products: the scoring scale assessment method and the acceptance test method. In the first phase, the composition of the team of evaluators was established. This was made up of 14 subjects, non-smokers, aged between 22-23 years, of which 12 were female and 2 were male.

Table 5. Sensorial analysis

No. crt	Attribute	Characteristics	Scores			
			P0 control	P1 – 1%	P2 – 3%	P3 – 5%
1	External and internal appearance (without tasting)	Crust colour	3.57	2.57	2.29	2.29
2		Crumb colour	3.43	3.07	3.07	3.21
3		Crumb pore uniformity	4.07	3.57	3.71	3.5
4		Crumb softness to the touch	4.00	3.36	2.93	2.86
5		Crumb crumbliness	3.29	3.14	3.14	2.71
6	Flavour (Basic tastes)	Bitter taste	1.64	1.93	2.14	2.93
		Salty taste	1.71	2.07	2.14	2.14
		Sour taste	1.21	1.71	2	2.57
		Specific aroma	2.29	2.43	2.93	4
7	After-taste	Flavour persistence after chewing and swallowing	2.29	2.14	2.57	3.29
8	Total acceptability	1.....9	7.14	6.14	6.07	6.07

The evaluation system used for the analysis of the sensory characteristics in the evaluation sheet was the 5-point one. Thus, the subjects had to give each characteristic a score on a scale from 1 to 5 according to their degree of intensity. The evaluation uses a hedonic scale with nine points and nine possible ratings for the evaluated product, ranging from “I like it very much” to “I dislike it very much”.

Fig. 3. Bakery products with added sea buckthorn powder

The results of the sensory analysis showed that the addition of 1% sea buckthorn powder favourably influenced the organoleptic index of the obtained sample. Considerable differences are recorded in terms of the crust colour, which is more intense compared to the control samples. Another difference was observed at the level of the crumb, which is elastic and has a well-developed porosity. The taste and aroma turned out to be pleasant.

Following the analysis, it was identified that with the addition of 5%, the taste is bitter and to the same extent sour, the aroma is specific to sea buckthorn, and its persistence after chewing and swallowing is very pronounced, similar results being obtained by Popa et al. (2022). In terms of porosity, it has been shown to be poorly developed, and overall acceptability is mildly pleasing.

We can see that there are significant differences regarding the control sample and the one with 5% sea buckthorn addition. One of the differences is at the level of the bitter, sour taste, but also the specific aroma of sea buckthorn. A significant difference compared to the control sample is regarding the persistence of the flavour after chewing and swallowing.

Fig. 4. Graphic representation of the results of the sensory analysis regarding total acceptability

Regarding the total degree of acceptability, it was found that the bread with the highest weight is the one with the addition of 1%, registering a percentage of 6.14% compared to the other samples with different additions. The other samples with 3% and 5% respectively were accepted in a proportion of 6.07% compared to the control sample which registered a percentage of 7.14%.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The results obtained in this study indicate that the use of sea buckthorn powder (derived from by-products) in proportions of 1% and 3% in bread dough has a favorable impact on the sensory characteristics of the final product. Samples P1 (1%) and P2 (3%) recorded high scores for parameters such as crumb color, elasticity, porosity, and aroma, maintaining a high level of consumer acceptability (81 and 75 points out of 100). This supports the idea that moderate additions of sea buckthorn by-products enhance both the nutritional value and sensory appeal of bakery products.

Compared to the specialized literature, the results confirm the findings of Popa et al. (2022), which showed that 1% and 2% additions of organic sea buckthorn powder increase the fiber and antioxidant content of bread without significantly affecting its organoleptic properties. Similarly, the study by Luntraru et al. (2022) demonstrated that sea buckthorn by-products (pulp and seeds) can be valorized as functional ingredients,

offering a high antioxidant profile and the ability to stabilize color and taste in bakery products.

Regarding the sensory analysis, the sample with 1% sea buckthorn addition achieved the highest degree of acceptability (6.14 on a 9-point hedonic scale), close to the control sample (7.14), confirming a good integration of this ingredient into the standard recipe. This observation aligns with the studies by Reynoso-Camacho et al. (2021), which state that small additions of fruit by-products (1–2%) can improve the aroma, color, and texture of bakery goods without compromising sensory acceptability.

On the other hand, the sample with 5% addition (P3) was characterized by a significant decrease in scores for volume, elasticity, and taste—results explained by the high concentration of acids, tannins, and bitter compounds specific to sea buckthorn. This trend is also reflected in other studies (Marcillo-Parra et al. 2021), which show that excessive additions of by-products from polyphenol-rich fruits may result in intense bitterness and a drier texture due to the high content of insoluble fibers.

Furthermore, the basic taste analysis confirmed the increased perception of bitter and sour notes at higher concentrations (5%), which negatively affected the aftertaste and overall acceptability—an observation similar to that reported by Piñat et al. (2014) in the context of using sea buckthorn seed oils.

Therefore, the data support the hypothesis that moderate additions (1–3%) of sea buckthorn by-products can be used to fortify bread, improving its content of nutrients (antioxidants, fiber, vitamins) without compromising sensory qualities. These results also demonstrate the practical application of circular economy principles and mountain bioeconomy in the bakery industry, helping to reduce food waste and fully valorize local resources.

In recent years, the bakery industry has increasingly turned to the valorization of berries such as blueberries, raspberries, blackberries, and sea buckthorn, due to their high content of antioxidants, fiber, vitamins, and other bioactive compounds. This trend is driven by several factors. Firstly, consumers are increasingly interested in healthy food products that support immunity, digestion, and the prevention of chronic diseases. Bread and other baked goods enriched with berries meet these needs through a superior nutritional profile.

Secondly, using by-products from fruit processing—such as pulp, seeds, or peels—contributes to reducing food waste and protecting the environment, in line with the principles of the circular economy. New technologies, such as drying, freeze-drying, and microencapsulation, allow the preservation of the nutritional value of these ingredients and their integration into bakery recipes without affecting the taste or texture of the final products.

Moreover, in Romania, the local availability of berries from both cultivated sources and wild mountain flora supports this type of food innovation. The trend of berry valorization in the bakery sector thus reflects a current direction in the food industry, where health, sustainability, and innovation go hand in hand.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrated that the use of sea buckthorn by-products in the bakery industry can represent a viable solution for the valorisation of local resources and the reduction of food waste, in accordance with the principles of the circular economy. Experimental tests have shown that an addition of 1% sea buckthorn powder gives the best results from an organoleptic point of view, improving the taste, aroma and texture of the bread, without negatively affecting the acceptability of the product. Higher additions (3% and 5%) were associated with an intensification of sour and bitter taste, which decreased the degree of acceptability. From a nutritional point of view, sea buckthorn bread provides a significant amount of antioxidants, vitamins and fibre, which places it in the category of functional foods with potential health benefits. These characteristics make sea buckthorn a valuable ingredient for the development of innovative and sustainable products in the food industry. The integration of sea buckthorn by-products in baking can contribute to diversifying the product offer, increasing the economic value of local resources and stimulating the rural economy, especially in mountainous areas. These results underline the need for continued research to optimize processes and expand the applications of sea buckthorn by-products in other sectors of the food industry.

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